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Executive Summary

This Knowledge and Information Sharing – Phase 2 report describes the Education and Dissemination activities and resources developed in the final 2.5 years of the HEAP project (Jan 2023 - June 2025). The strategy for the activities remained focused on synergies between education, dissemination and communication activities to enable the target audiences to learn and be informed, while generating lasting and widely accessible educational and dissemination material. The focus was also to expand target audiences and ensure wide and sustainable promotion of the outputs of the HEAP project, guided by the conclusions of the HEAP project reviews in 2023 and 2024.

Two scientific symposia—a Consumer Purchase Data Symposium and the final HEAP Symposium, “Humanity and the Environment: Moving Exposome Research from Information to Action,” were the main learning and informational events targeting researchers during Phase 2.

Both Symposia featured guest speakers from beyond the HEAP Consortia and focused on outreach to a broader audience, including researchers from the EHEN network and BCNet (an IARC-led international network). To enable wider dissemination, a series of videos was created from the presentations of these events.

The HEAP seminar series on Ethics and Regulations had a similar broad target audience of exposome researchers. It presented learnings from the HEAP projects on governance of exposome research projects and the use of wearable sensors in observational research, with the recordings available via the HEAP and EHEN toolboxes.

Two further Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops (#4 and #5), jointly organised by WPs 7, 11, and 1, gave the data providers a forum to test and demonstrate the features of the HEAP platform. Regarding FAIR Data principles in practice, a workshop with WP7 was held at IARC, and materials were made available on the “Resources” page of the HEAP website.

Scientific publications from the HEAP pilot projects presented results from bioinformatics pipelines, with links published on the HEAP and EHEN websites for other researchers to use. There was also a promotional campaign for some ground-breaking HEAP research on HPV vaccinations. A LinkedIn page was launched to expand the HEAP network of researchers and citizen scientists, and WP11 played a key role in coordinating the final EHEN policy brief.

Phase 2 marked a concerted effort from WP11 to connect with study participants from the HEAP pilot projects, citizen scientists, and young people. Another key aim of Phase 2 activities was to address the

sustainability of the HEAP platform beyond the project duration, clarifying long-term support mechanisms and relevant maintenance strategies.

Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Target audiences	6
2. Learning and informational events for researchers	6
EHEN Scientific Meeting 2023	6
Consumer Data Symposium 2023	6
HEAP final Symposium “From Information to Action”	7
HEAP Seminar series on Legal, Ethical and Governance Challenges in exposome research	8
Bring Your Own Data workshops	9
Technical training workshop - secure infrastructure	9
Technical training workshop - FAIR data principles in practice	10
Exposome Moonshot Forum - May 2025	10
3. Learning and informational events for citizen scientists	11
School outreach - exposome concept	11
School outreach - what is a biobank?	13
School outreach - CSI return visit to IARC	13
Public outreach - Fetes Consulaires	15
4. Learning and informational resources	16
Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.	16
Policy issues	16
Scientific publications	16
Resources for citizen scientists	16
5. Communication channels	17
Annex 1: Promotional posters	18
Annex 2: HEAP Symposium brochure	21
Annex 3: Fair data principles in practice - training course agenda	21
Annex 4: EHEN policy brief	22

1. Target audiences

Building on the target audience mapping conducted during WP11 Phase 1 (for Epidemiologists, Biologists/medical researchers, biobank managers and applied AI users and documented in Deliverable 11.3), during Phase 2, the WP11 team focused on expanding the researcher target audience group in Europe and internationally. These efforts focused on exposome researchers linked to the EHEN and IHEN consortia, and IARC's BCNet network. Channels used included the BCNet and HEAP e-newsletters, the EHEN website events page and Communication and Dissemination Working Group channels, an EHEN-wide policy brief, and international scientific outreach via the Exposome Moonshot Forum, which featured a presentation from Zisis Kozlakidis, scientific lead of the WP11 Work Package.

The activities outlined in this report were also designed in response to feedback from the HEAP project reviews in 2023 and 2024, specifically around enhancing efforts to reach hard-to-reach audiences through diverse platforms. The WP11 team targeted new audiences via an on-line survey on the Exposome aimed at citizen scientists, inviting a student group from a Dutch University to the IARC Nouveau Centre, initiating a partnership with school local to IARC (WP11 lead institution), participation in the Lyon Fetes Consulaires via an exhibition stand, and making a pitch to a science website with a wide audience to produce a video on the Exposome.

The HEAP Sustainability Plan (deliverable 1.2) outlines further information on WP11's role in ensuring the sustainability of dissemination and communication activities to target audiences.

2. Learning and informational events for researchers

EHEN Scientific Meeting 2023

Held in May 2023, WP11 produced posters focusing on the HEAP pilot projects and promoting the FAIR data tutorials for the exhibition following the presentation of abstracts from HEAP researchers. The target audience was researchers from the EHEN projects. See Annex 1 for the posters.

Consumer Data Symposium 2023

Held in September 2023, the "First International Consumer Data Symposium," hosted by WP4 at Statens Serum Institut and co-organised with WP11, explored the wide array of ways CPD can be used to improve public health and ensure consumer safety.

The Symposium featured presentations from four researchers external to the project, including from the USA, who are also working with this new type of data. Topics included how Consumer Purchase Data is being used to support outbreak investigations, and how it can provide insights into the health impacts of our diets and exposures to chemicals in everyday products.

Panel discussions addressed research challenges related to working with consumer purchase data, inconsistencies in naming conventions, and the future use of CPD in public health and research.

The HEAP WP4 team presented their GDPR-compliant, secure, encrypted web application solution developed with HEAP WP2 as part of the Consumer Purchase Data pilot project, to enable consumers to consent to share their consumer data with researchers.

WP11 packaged the presentations from the Symposium on the HEAP website/YouTube channel: <https://heap-exposome.eu/consumer-purchase-data-symposium/>

HEAP final Symposium “From Information to Action”

The final HEAP Symposium, entitled "Humanity and the Environment: Moving Exposome Research from Information to Action," was held in May 2024 at IARC's Nouveau Centre. It was aimed at exposome researchers, ethicists, and policymakers and featured talks and insights on exposome research infrastructures and data, public health ethics, governance of research projects, and engagement with research participants.

The theme of Day 1 was "Research infrastructures and data: Advancing knowledge on the environment and our health" and featured a tour of the IARC biobank and a keynote from Jana Klánová, coordinator of EIRENE (Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure). Through a series of presentations, HEAP researchers demonstrated how exposome data from wearable devices, consumer receipts and biological samples can be harnessed for scientific insights. The day concluded with a plenary discussion on the impact and potential of collaborative exposome research.

Day 2: "Exposome research: Ethics, Law and Future Perspectives" consisted of three sessions, "Exposome research and public health ethics", "Governance of research projects", and "Future enablers of exposome research", featuring presentations on EU ethical and legal topics in exposome research, public health and health equity, open science and cross-border research, engagement with study participants, and the European Health Data Space.

In keeping with the focus on expanding the HEAP target audiences, the Symposium concluded with an international perspective on biobanking from guest speakers from the IARC-led BCNet and a presentation about the new International Human Exposome Network (IHEN).

WP11 packaged the presentations from the Symposium on the HEAP website/YouTube channel:

<https://heap-exposome.eu/heap-symposium-2024/>

See Annex 2 for the HEAP Symposium brochure.

HEAP Seminar series on Legal, Ethical and Governance Challenges in exposome research

Held in June 2025, these webinars targeted international exposome researchers from EHEN and BCNet. IARC will host a third webinar via IHEN in Q3 as part of the HEAP sustainability plan.

Seminar 1: Towards Ethical Exposome Research: Challenges and Solutions in Data Protection and Governance, was presented by Daniel Groos of HEAP WP2.

Based on experience from HEAP, this session offered practical guidance to exposome researchers on managing sensitive data in compliance with evolving legal and ethical standards. It also offered key lessons from specific legal tasks, including strategies for the safe transfer of data to third countries and the development of a sustainable governance framework.

The session also explored exposome research in the context of the right to health, showing how participant-centered governance models can foster ethical engagement and public trust, and concluded with a forward-looking discussion on the future of exposome research, focusing on the potential role of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) in supporting its advancement.

Seminar 2: From Wrist to Research: The Responsible Use of Wearables in Observational Studies, was presented by Evert-Ben Van Veen, the HEAP WP2 lead.

It covered responsible data practices and participant protections in wearable-based research, grounded in insights from the European Human Exposome Network Ethics and Law Working Group.

The webinar explored the legal and ethical dimensions of using commercial wearables, such as smartwatches, in observational research.

outlined the conditions under which wearable data can be responsibly integrated into research and offered practical insights into reconciling innovation with compliance and public trust.

The first two HEAP Seminars attracted 120 attendees. As part of the sustainability plan, the recordings will be available via the online toolboxes for EHEN and HEAP.

Bring Your Own Data workshops

In the final 30 months of the project, the WP7 and WP11 teams held two Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) workshops. These workshops are essential elements of the HEAP project and designed to collectively develop, test, and gather feedback on the HEAP platform.

The fourth HEAP Bring Your Own Data (BYOD#4) workshop, held in Helsinki in November 2024, enabled hands-on collaboration between HEAP exposome researchers, software developers, IT infrastructure specialists and legal experts to test and demonstrate the HEAP platform in practical exposome research.

During the workshop, researchers uploaded and analysed datasets from the Swedish cervical screening cohort, comprising over 3 million anonymised data points. From a data governance viewpoint, this cohort also tested Digital Use Conditions (DUCs), which, along with Common Conditions of Use Elements (CCEs), can be used to catalogue resources and define access permissions and conditions of data reuse.

Researchers also used environmental data, comprising deep-sequenced metagenomic samples of microbes from sewage samples from 19 Swedish cities that were originally used to identify the presence of the COVID-19 virus during the pandemic. During hands-on sessions, these datasets were used to train Machine Learning (ML) prediction models for cervical cancer incidence, and to monitor SARS-CoV-2 presence in sewage samples. The demonstrated tools and pipelines, as well as the ML models, stimulated collaboration among the participants to find solutions for improvements and reuse.

The fifth and final BYOD workshop focused on demonstrating the project's main technical achievements, the sustainability of the HEAP cohorts data, including the final validation of the HEAP cohorts by DUCs and data FAIRness, the sustainability of the HEAP platform, and conditions in which researchers beyond the consortia can access it (see Sustainability Plan D1.2 for more details).

Tools tested and validated during the BYOD workshops are featured in the final version of the EHEN online toolbox and the HEAP online toolbox.

<https://heap-exposome.eu/toolbox/>

<https://www.humanexposome.eu/toolbox/>

The software tools, including the PaaS, are accessible from the Elixir Toolbox (also documented in D2.1), and HEAP shareable legacy data from the wearable devices and environmental data (DNA and mass spec from waste water from Sweden) are accessible through the HEAP instance of Hopsworks in CSC infrastructure.

Technical training workshop - secure infrastructure

An online training workshop for HEAP data providers regarding the secure infrastructure hosted at CSC (WP10) took place in Q1 2023. Materials were made available via the toolboxes mentioned above for a wider audience. The content focused on creating an account with CSC, setting up your private workspace with SD services, and accessing data using SD Desktop.

Technical training workshop - FAIR data principles in practice

IARC hosted the training course in November 2023. It focused on interoperability and the reuse of scientific data and was aimed at scientific researchers, bioinformaticians, and data scientists. The course comprised a self-study element based on the FAIR data video tutorials developed by HEAP in 2022, followed by a two-day, in-person workshop at the IARC Nouveau Centre in Lyon, France.

Following the initial workshop in Lyon and considering feedback from participants and facilitators, the "FAIR Data Principles in Practice" course is part of a broader learning path on Open Science that IARC is currently developing. Online elements of this learning path will be open access and available via the IARC Learning Platform (<https://learning.iarc.fr/>), soon to be migrated to the WHO Learning Academy online platform (<https://www.who.int/about/who-academy>).

See Annexe 3 for the agenda.

Exposome Moonshot Forum - May 2025

As part of sustainability of the outputs of the HEAP project, Dr Zisis Kozlakidis, scientific lead for HEAP WP11 and Head of Laboratory Support, Biobanking, and Services at the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), presented details of the ongoing Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP) and International Human Exposome Network (IHEN) projects at the inaugural Exposome Moonshot Forum, which took place on 12–15 May 2025 in Washington DC, USA. The aim of the Forum was to develop a clear and actionable plan for the comprehensive characterisation and utilisation of the human exposome.

More than 300 international stakeholders from 30 countries, including experts in different parts of the exposome field, convened at the Forum, which focused on collaborations and advances in future exposome research. The participants included stakeholders from the World Health Organization (WHO), the United States National Institutes of Health (NIH), and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), as well as national experts from Canada, France, Greece, the Netherlands, Romania, and the United Kingdom, among others.

3. Learning and informational events for citizen scientists

School outreach - exposome concept

Phase 2 saw target audiences expand to include a general audience, including students and young people. WP11 initiated a partnership with Cité Scolaire Internationale to target the 11-15 age group.

The first visit took place in June 2024. The teaching materials (presentation and notes) were presented to 250 students in four sessions of 50 minutes each, and the reusable content (presentation and notes) is summarised in the table below. The teaching materials feature in the online toolboxes as part of the sustainability plan.

The exposome – citizen science engagement

Schools outreach session

Target audience	Secondary school children (age 11-16)
Learning objectives:	<p>An understanding of the exposome concept and some of the environmental factors that can affect our health</p> <p>Overview of some scientific research projects on the exposome</p> <p>Understanding how scientific researchers think up research questions</p> <p>Practice asking follow-up questions on research projects.</p>
Session format and structure	<p>50-minute group lesson (group size 15-40)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • resentation to the full group • roup challenges: Small group discussions, “post-it” notes, verbal feedback to the full group, full group discussion, Q&A <p>Follow-up activities: tbc</p>
Materials	PowerPoint slides, A1 paper, coloured post-it notes and pens
Subjects	<p>Part 1: (15 -20 mins) Introduction</p> <p>“How does the environment affect our health?” – get ideas from the class and feedback on their survey responses</p> <p>How do we find out more about this?</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to scientific institutions, WHO, IARC, SSI and Universities (1 slide)• Profiles of people who work in these scientific institutions (researchers, communicators) <p>Examples of our scientific projects (3 slides)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Wearable data• Consumer data• Science communication (Your Exposome survey) <p>Part 2: (15-20 mins) Group challenges</p> <p>1 large sheets of paper for each challenge. Groups write answers on post-it notes and stick them on.</p> <p>Challenge 1 – You’re a science communicator preparing for an interview with Frederik or Allison, researchers using consumer and wearable data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Write down a question you would like to ask them about their job or their research project that has just been presented.• How would you make sure your friends got to hear about the interview? How would you present it? (eg Video? Audio? In writing?) How would you distribute it? (Social media? Magazine? Book?) <p>Challenge 2a - Think up a new research question using wearable data. What do you think Allison could research next?</p> <p>Challenge 2b –Think up a new research question using consumer data. What do you think Frederik could research next?</p> <p>Part 3: (15 minutes) – Feedback/ discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rep from each group feeds back on the results of the challenge
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School outreach - what is a biobank?

In June 2025, another visit took place for presenting biobanking in the context of broad consent to 200 students ahead of a visit to the IARC biobank.

Photo: IARC WP11 presenter at the CSI

A key message was to stress the importance of broad consent as an enabler for research using biobanking. Biobanking has the **FUTURE** in mind. This means that when samples are collected, researchers don't know what scientific discoveries they will lead to. They **DO** know they will be useful, but they don't fully know, at the time of collection, what they could be useful for. It's important that the people giving samples understand that the samples they are contributing have value not just in the present, but for the future.

School outreach - CSI return visit to IARC

During their visit in June 2025, 58 students toured the biobank and laboratories and learned how citizens participate in and contribute to scientific research by donating biological samples and sharing their personal health data.

The visit included a debating exercise on the pros and cons of broad consent, with the majority of students agreeing that with appropriate safeguards, they would willingly donate biological samples for scientific research.

Details of the activity included:

20-Minute Activity: Debate and Safeguard Building

Step 1: Divide and Debate (10 minutes)

- Split the class into **two groups**:
 - **Group A: "For Broad Consent"**
 - **Group B: "Against Broad Consent"**
- Give each group 5 minutes to prepare 2–3 key points to support their side using their prep notes.
- Each group presents their arguments (2 minutes per group).
- 5 minutes of questions to the other group

Step 2: Safeguard Suggestions (10 minutes)

- As a whole class, lead a brainstorm: **"If we were designing our own biobank, what rules would we put in place to make sure people feel safe giving broad consent?"**

Write down ideas on the board or a poster.

Prompt with examples like:

- Only approved researchers can access the data.
- Participants can withdraw at any time.
- Vote – how comfortable would you feel giving broad consent (10 - very comfortable, 0 – not at all) – Stick on board (results below)

The visit ended with an interactive careers Q&A session, during which IARC scientists described their day-to-day jobs, education, and career paths.

The visit is described on LinkedIn via the Link below:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7341119761533054976/>

All materials are reusable and available on the HEAP and EHEN toolboxes.

Public outreach - Fetes Consulaires

In June 2025, representatives from HEAP WP11 attended a public outreach event in Lyon (Fetes Consulaires) to carry this same message about the IARC biobank to local citizens (400 reached).

4. Learning and informational resources

Data privacy regulation, ethical and legal issues.

As part of their leadership of the EHEN Ethics and Law working group, materials were published on the EHEN website and online toolbox as follows:

- A blog article for the EHEN website.
- A document with a summary of issues and activities on Ethics and Law related to the entire EHEN network and exposome research
- The HEAP seminar series (as part of the HEAP Sustainability Plan)

Policy issues

WP11 also coordinated the production of the final published EHEN policy brief, which included a section relating to Health Data Management. (see Annex 4)

Scientific publications

HEAP research featured in scientific journals, with key publications captured on the toolbox page of the HEAP website and promoted via the HEAP project LinkedIn page.

Notable publications included research using HEAP cohort data on gender neutral HPV vaccination:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128055058595745793/>

Rapid HPV genotype detection:

<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7318283436589248514/>

Resources for citizen scientists

In an effort to reach wider audiences, further resources developed by WP11 included the first-ever public survey on the exposome aimed at a general population:

<https://survey.alchemer.com/s3/7571782/Exposome>

It provided valuable information on public perceptions of health/environmental interactions and their view of the potential public good of exposome research.

<https://heap-exposome.eu/2024/01/25/results-from-the-first-ever-public-survey-on-the-exposome/>

5. Communication channels

The table below details the main external communication channels and their strategic purpose in promoting project goals.

Channel	Strategic approach	Strategic purpose
HEAP website https://heap-exposome.eu/	-Provide key, publicly available project information -Provide access to learning resources via a learning platform linked to IARC learning -Later in the project, differentiate parts of the website by stakeholder group (public, policymaker, researcher, etc.)	-To serve as the main public face of the HEAP project, open to all audiences and delivering all the project's key messages. -Able to evolve with the project, as new content becomes available and stakeholder groups evolve.
HEAP LinkedIn account	Content is easily shareable by HEAP consortia members	To support the building of an engaged exposome community
HEAP YouTube channel https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCvTOwwydTW4WcFO6b4kEcVg	Hosting of tutorial videos on legal/ethical, FAIR data and technical aspects of HEAP, and informational videos about the progress of the project	To support the building of an engaged exposome community
European Human Exposome Network website https://www.humanexposome.eu/	To serve as a common focus and source of information and news for all the projects in the network.	-To aggregate common information on the exposome -To reduce duplication of content across EHEN project websites -To amplify the common messages of all EHEN projects

Annex 1: Promotional posters

Snapshots of promotional posters produced by WP11 in collaboration with the HEAP pilot projects for EHEN Scientific meeting 2023:

HEAP PROJECT OVERVIEW

A reproducible, scalable platform for exposome research

Building on previous EU Horizon 2020 projects

such as B3Africa, RD-Connect, and FP7 BiobankCloud, HEAP aims to provide an open-access, technical research platform to assess the impact of the exposome on human health, scalable to any research setting.

The HEAP Data Life-Cycle

New insights through deep learning and advanced analytics

HEAP's SME partner, Hopsworks, is working with HEAP researchers to extend the Hopsworks PaaS to accommodate data warehousing and allow stream processing to capture real-time data.

3-minute video about HEAP and Hopsworks

The HEAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme under grant agreement No 874662.

HEAP LEARNING RESOURCES

The “Swamped?” video series 5-minute adventures in data management

FAIR frog and Data Gator are scientific researchers from two very different institutions – Swamp Institute, and FAIR Labs...

Through their adventures, they show us why FAIR data principles are essential for open science, and for managing the ever-larger datasets available to researchers.

“Swamped?” is an engaging overview of the data management skills every scientist should have.

Watch on the HEAP
YouTube channel

The HEAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme under grant agreement No 874662.

HEAP CONSUMER COHORT STUDY

Using consumer purchase data to assess the external household exposome

The "My Purchases" cohort

PI: Frederik Trier Møller
frtm@ssi.dk

**Cohort registration
and FAQ webpage**

The HEAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme under grant agreement No 874662.

HEAP WEARABLE COHORT

Longitudinal exposome profiling using wearable device metagenome and metabolome data

Wearable cohort of pregnant women

- Proof-of-concept exposure study of 100 pregnant/non-pregnant Finnish women

The HEAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research programme under grant agreement No 874662.

Annex 2: HEAP Symposium brochure

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1_I9UtPpkPR3doNZiToWxXexqjHPQGaD5/view?usp=drive_link

Annex 3: Fair data principles in practice - training course agenda

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1JTEJCdEN0Gpc-BxyV0vtqSyKKCSzyxl7/view?usp=drive_link

Annex 4: EHEN policy brief

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1cYem5aKEndl0bJNQgmzr5J9gjs847fD1/view?usp=drive_link